

PATHWAYS OF UNINTENTIONAL INTRODUCTION AND SPREAD OF 114 INVASIVE ALIEN SPECIES OF UNION CONCERN IN BELGIUM

IDENTIFICATION AND PRIORITIZATION

National Scientific Secretariat on Invasive Alien Species
2026

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This report is an update of the 2018, 2020 and 2023 Belgian reports on identification and prioritization of introduction pathways of invasive alien species (IAS) of Union Concern, which considered respectively the 49, 66 and 88 species that were listed that time. This updated report includes the 26 species that were added to the list in August 2025 and thus considers a total of 114 species, representing all the species of the Union list at the time of writing (May 2026).

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Summary

Article 13 of the Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species (the 'IAS Regulation') requires Member States to identify and prioritize pathways of unintentional introduction and spread of IAS of Union Concern. This report identifies priority pathways of unintentional introduction in Belgium for the 114 IAS of Union Concern listed to date (2026).

Pathways were identified using EU risk assessments and the CBD classification framework (Harrower et al., 2018; CBD, 2014) while their relevance for Belgium was assessed using expert judgement. A prioritization was then carried out based on species' impact, establishment potential and the frequency of introduction via the identified pathway.

The results confirm strong consistency with previous prioritization analyses (NSSIAS, 2018, 2020 and 2023). The same top 12 pathways are identified for the 114-species dataset, with only minor rank shifts. Natural dispersal, pet/aquarium/terrarium trade and ornamental plants (other than horticulture) remain the dominant pathways. Notable increases are observed for transport of habitat material and machinery while aquatic stowaway pathways show slight decrease in relative importance. No new pathways were identified compared to the previous analysis.

When focusing on species not yet established in Belgium, additional attention is drawn to contaminated goods and international transport vectors (pathways: containers and ballast water), alongside the continued importance of natural dispersal and escape pathways. These results highlight the need for strengthened cross-border cooperation and improved surveillance at key entry points.

Overall, the findings indicate that the current National Action Plan on priority pathways remains broadly adequate, as it already addresses the most high-ranking pathways. However, emerging priorities – particularly container transport and certain contaminant pathways – may warrant targeted adjustments or additional operational measures. Continuous improvement of data on pathways and introduction events is a key requirement to further refine prioritization and strengthen prevention.

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1. Scope

The present report constitutes the third Belgian prioritization of pathways of IAS of Union Concern in accordance with Article 13 of the European Regulation 1143/2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species. It includes the 26 species that were added on the Union list following its update which entered into force on 7th of August 2025. This report should be considered a working document and will be updated as new species are added to the list of species of Union Concern, or as new knowledge on species and pathways necessitates a revision of the prioritization exercise. The current version presents the analysis and results of the prioritization exercise taking into account all invasive alien species (IAS) of Union concern listed to date (May 2026).

An excel spreadsheet containing all the raw data on species and their pathways used in this report is publicly available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20125708>.

2. Background

Invasive alien species sensu EU Regulation are organisms that are – accidentally or deliberately – introduced by human activity outside their natural range, and whose introduction has been found to threaten or adversely impact upon biodiversity and ecosystem services (provisioning, regulating, habitat and/or cultural). They are considered as one of the most important direct drivers of loss of ecosystem services and biodiversity (Brunel et al., 2013) and have been identified as number one driver of changes in species' traits (Jaureguiberry et al., 2022). The incidence and impact of IAS are only expected to increase in the future (Dudley et al., 2010; Mormul et al., 2022).

Invasive alien species represent a threat to native plants and animals in Europe. While there is a need for greater transparency and rigor when estimating costs of biological invasions (Hulme et al., 2024), IAS are estimated to cause damage worth billions of euros to the European economy every year. Estimated costs between 1960 and 2020 summed to €116.61 billion, with the majority (60%) being damage-related and impacting multiple sectors (Haubrock et al., 2021). The comprehensive IPBES Assessment Report on IAS and their control (2023) states that they cost humanity more than \$400 billion a year from 2019 onwards – and that damage is accelerating with likely costs quadrupling every decade. The “*Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species*” (the ‘IAS Regulation’) is a response at the European level to the threat posed by IAS. It entered into force on 1 January 2015 and seeks to address the problem of IAS in a comprehensive manner, preventing, minimising and mitigating the adverse effects of IAS on native biodiversity and related ecosystem services. The IAS Regulation is primarily aimed at minimizing the spread of IAS which represent a substantial threat to biodiversity and related ecosystem services in (parts of) Europe. It therefore establishes a list of species of concern to the European Union (the Union List species), for which a set of prohibitions and measures apply. As new IAS can be introduced into the Union and alien species already present are spreading and expanding their range, the list is dynamic and allows for regular updating. Species can be proposed for inclusion on the list at the initiative of Member States or the European Commission.

The IAS Regulation foresees a three-stage hierarchical approach based on 1) prevention, 2) early detection and rapid eradication, and 3) control and/or containment. This approach aims at minimising new introductions, subsequent establishment and covers management of already established invasive species. It reflects scientific and policy consensus that prevention is generally far more cost-effective and environmentally desirable than post-introduction measures (Leung et al., 2002; Finoff et al., 2007; Kim et al., 2016; Cuthbert et al., 2022). Where prevention failed and an IAS has been introduced, early detection (backed by early warning and information exchange) and rapid eradication drastically minimise costs associated with the invasion (Ahmed, 2021). If eradication is not feasible, control and/or containment measures should be implemented in a timely matter to steeply reduce long term economic impacts (Ahmed, 2021).

Here, we address pathway analysis as a component of prevention. The importance of considering pathways is widely acknowledged as a key element of prevention (Wittenberg et al., 2005; Hulme, 2009; McGeogh et al., 2016; Matthews et al., 2017). At international and European level, several policy measures are already in place tackling pathways via which IAS are introduced, e.g. the Ballast Water Convention, (standards from) the International Plant Protection Convention, the World Trade Organization's Agreement on the Application of Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures, the OIE standards (World Organization for Animal Health), the EU Aquaculture Regulation and the Wildlife Trade Regulation. In addition, introduction pathways of IAS are also addressed in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), under Target 6: "Reduce rates of introduction and establishment of invasive alien species by 50 per cent by 2030".

The IAS Regulation forbids transport, breeding, keeping, selling, exchanging and releasing listed species, thereby covering intentional pathways of introduction of IAS. However, a large proportion of IAS are also introduced unintentionally (CBD, 2014), and for some taxa these so-called unintentional pathways are more prevalent than intentional pathways (Saul et al., 2017). Unintentionally introduced species can be even more costly (Turbelin et al., 2022) and harder to manage in the new environment than intentionally introduced species (Pysec et al., 2011).

Globally, the most common invasion routes of vertebrates and plants consist of an intentional entry into captive holding with subsequent escape or release into the environment. While plants usually spread beyond gardens and parks where they were originally planted via natural dispersal or dumping of green waste, animals either escape captivity or are dumped by irresponsible owners. On the contrary, most invasive invertebrates, algae, microorganisms and fungi tend to arrive as the result of contamination of a certain good or as a stowaway (Hulme, 2008; Saul et al., 2017). Invasions through transport corridors such as canals, bridges, tunnels and roadsides are also important pathways (Brisson et al., 2010; Nunes et al., 2015; Saul et al., 2017) that are often underestimated (Hulme, 2008).

Therefore, according to Article 13 of the IAS Regulation, Member States must identify and prioritize unintentional introduction pathways for IAS for their countries and develop actions to prevent further introductions. More specifically, article 13 requires Member States to: "*carry out a comprehensive analysis of the pathways of unintentional introduction and spread of invasive alien species of Union concern at least in their territory, as well as in their marine waters as defined in point (1) of Article 3 of Directive 2008/56/EC, and identify the pathways which require priority action ('priority pathways') because of the volume of species or of the potential damage caused by the species entering the Union through those pathways.*"

After prioritization, each Member state has to establish and implement (a set of) action plans to address the priority pathways it has identified in their country specific analysis.

3. Methodology for identification and prioritization of introduction pathways in Belgium

The process of identification and prioritization of the pathways of introduction for Belgium involved the following steps:

- 1) Pathway identification: the production of a Belgian inventory of pathways of introduction and spread IAS of Union Concern.
- 2) Development of a prioritization method.
- 3) Application of developed method to introduction and spread pathways for IAS of Union Concern.

3.1. Species considered

The species covered by this pathway analysis are all 114 species of Union Concern to date (2026): (TABLE 1). These include the species of Implementing Regulation (EU) N° 2016/1141 (37 species), Implementing Regulation (EU) N° 2017/1263 (12 species), Implementing Regulation (EU) N° 2019/1262 (17 species), Implementing Regulation (EU) N° 2022/1203 (22 species) and Implementing Regulation (EU) N° 2025/1422.

Table 1. The 114 invasive alien species of Union concern considered in this study. "IR" indicates the year of the implementing regulation via which the species was added to the list of IAS of Union Concern: 2016 - IR (EU) n° 2016/1141; 2017 - IR (EU) n° 2017/1263; 2019 - IR (EU) n° 2019/1262; 2022 - IR (EU) n° 2022/1203; 2025 - IR (EU) N° 2025/1422. "***": the species is unlikely to establish in Belgium under current climatical conditions.

Scientific name	Common name (Dutch)	Common name (French)	IR
<i>Acacia mearnsii</i> [as 'mearnsi'] De Wild., Pl. Bequaert. 3: 61 (1925)	Bleekgele acacia	Acacia noir	2025*
<i>Acacia saligna</i> (Labill.) H.L.Wendl. (<i>Acacia cyanophylla</i> Lindl.)	Wilgacacia	Mimosa bleuâtre	2019*
<i>Acridotheres cristatellus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Kuifmaina	Martin huppé	2025
<i>Acridotheres tristis</i> Linnaeus, 1766	Treurmaina	Martin triste	2019
<i>Ailanthus altissima</i> (Mill.) Swingle	Hemelboom	Ailante glanduleux	2019
<i>Alopochen aegyptiacus</i> Linnaeus, 1766	Nijlgans	Ouette d'Egypte	2017
<i>Alternanthera philoxeroides</i> (Mart.) Griseb.	Alligatorkruid	Herbe à alligator	2017*
<i>Ameiurus melas</i> (Rafinesque, 1820)	Zwarte dwergmeerval	Poisson-chat commun	2022
<i>Andropogon virginicus</i> L. (Dendy, 1894) Jones & Gerard (1999)	Amerikaans bezemgras	Barbon de virginie	2019*
<i>Arthurdendylus triangulatus</i>	Nieuw-Zeelandse platworm	Ver plat de Nouvelle--Zélande	2019

<i>Asclepias syriaca</i> L.	Zijdeplant	Asclépiade de Syrie	2017
<i>Asterias amurensis</i> Lutken, 1871	Noord-Atlantische zeester	Étoile de mer du Pacifique Nord	2025
<i>Axis axis</i> (Erxleben, 1777)	Axishert	Cerf axis	2022
<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i> L.	Struikaster	Séneçon en arbre	2016
<i>Bipalium kewense</i> Moseley, 1868	Hamerhoofdlandplatworm	Ver plat à tête de marteau	2025
<i>Brachyponera chinensis</i> (Emery, 1895)		Fourmi à aiguillon	2025*
<i>Broussonetia papyrifera</i> (L.) L'Hér ex Vent.	Papiermoerbe	Mûrier à papier	2025
<i>Cabomba caroliniana</i> Gray	Waterwaaier	Cabomba de Caroline	2016
<i>Callosciurus erythraeus</i> Pallas, 1779	Pallas' eekhoorn	Ecureuil de Pallas	2016
<i>Callosciurus finlaysonii</i> (Horsfield, 1823)	Thaise eekhoorn	Écureuil de Finlayson	2022*
<i>Cardiospermum grandiflorum</i> Sw.	Ballonrank	Corinde à grandes fleurs	2019*
<i>Castor canadensis</i> Kuhl, 1820	Canadese bever	Castor du Canada	2025
<i>Celastrus orbiculatus</i> Thunb.	Aziatische boomwurjer	Célastre asiatique	2027
<i>Cervus nippon</i> Temminck, 1838	Sikahert	Cerf sika	2025
<i>Channa argus</i> (Cantor, 1842)	Noordelijke slangekopvis	Poisson à tête de serpent du Nord	2022
<i>Cherax destructor</i> Clark, 1936	Australische kreeft	Ecrevisse de Murray	2025*
<i>Cipangopaludina chinensis</i> (Gray 1834)	Chinese moeraslak	Paludine chinoise	2025
<i>Cortaderia jubata</i> (Lemoine ex Carrière) Stapf	Hoog pampasgras	Herbe de la pampa pourpre	2019
<i>Corvus splendens</i> Vieillot	Huiskraai	Corbeau familier	2016
<i>Crassula helmsii</i> (Kirk) Cockayne	Watercrassula	Crassule des étangs	2025
<i>Delairea odorata</i> Lem.	Klimopkruiskruid	Séneçon grim pant	2025
<i>Ehrharta calycina</i> Sm.	Roze rimpelgras	Ehrharte calycinale	2019*
<i>Elodea nuttallii</i> (Planch.) St. John	Smalle waterpest	Elodée de Nuttall	2017
<i>Eriocheir sinensis</i> H. Milne Edwards, 1854	Chinese wolhandkrab	Crabe chinois	2016
<i>Faxonius immunis</i> (Hagen, 1870)	Calicotrivierkreeft	Ecrevisse calicot	2025*
<i>Faxonius limosus</i> Rafinesque, 1817	Gevlekte Amerikaanse rivierkreeft	Ecrevisse américaine	2016
<i>Faxonius rusticus</i> (Girard, 1852)	Roestbruine Amerikaanse rivierkreeft	Écrevisse à taches rouges	2022

<i>Faxonius virilis</i> Hagen, 1802	Geknobbelde Amerikaanse rivierkreeft	Ecrevisse à pinces bleues	2016
<i>Fundulus heteroclitus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	<i>Fundulus heteroclitus</i>	Choquemort	2024
<i>Gambusia affinis</i> (Baird & Girard, 1853)	Westelijk muskietenvisje	Gambusie de l'Ouest	2022
<i>Gambusia holbrooki</i> Girard, 1859	Oostelijk muskietenvisje	Gambusie de l'Est	2022
<i>Gunnera tinctoria</i> (Molina) Mirbel	Chileense reuzenrabarber	Rhubarbe géante du Chili	2017*
<i>Gymnocoronis spilanthoides</i> (D. Don ex Hook. & Arn.) DC.	Smalle theeplant	Faux hygrophile	2019
<i>Hakea sericea</i> Schrad. & J.C.Wendl.	Hakea	Hakéa soyeux	2022
<i>Heracleum mantegazzianum</i> Sommier & Levier	Reuzenberenklauw	Berce du Caucase	2017
<i>Heracleum persicum</i> Fischer	Perzische berenklauw	Berce de Perse	2016
<i>Heracleum sosnowskyi</i> Mandenova	Sosnowsky's berenklauw	Berce de Sosnowski	2016
<i>Herpestes javanicus</i> É. Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, 1818	Indische mangoeste	Mangouste	2016*
<i>Humulus scandens</i> (Lour.) Merr.	Oosterse hop	Houblon du japon	2019*
<i>Hydrocotyle ranunculoides</i> L. f.	Grote waternavel	Hydrocotyle fausse renoncule	2016
<i>Impatiens glandulifera</i> Royle	Reuzenbalsemien	Balsamine de l'Himalaya	2017
<i>Koenigia polystachya</i> (Wall. ex Meisn.) T.M. Schust. & Reveal	Afghaanse duizendknoop	Renouée à nombreux épis	2022
<i>Lagarosiphon major</i> (Ridley) Moss	Verspreidbladige waterpest	Elodée à feuilles alternes	2016
<i>Lampropeltis getula</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Konings slang	Serpent roi de Californie	2022*
<i>Lepomis gibbosus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Zonnebaars	Perche soleil	2019
<i>Lespedeza cuneata</i> (Dum.Cours.) G. Don (Lespedeza juncea var. sericea (Thunb.) Lace & Hauech)	Chinese struikklaver	Lespedeza soyeux	2019
<i>Limnoperna fortunei</i> (Dunker, 1857)	Gouden mossel	Moule pygmée	2022*
<i>Lithobates (Rana) catesbeianus</i> Shaw, 1802	Amerikaanse stierkikker	Grenouille taureau	2016
<i>Ludwigia grandiflora</i> (Michx.) Greuter & Burdet	Grote waterteunisbloem	Jussie à grandes fleurs	2016
<i>Ludwigia peploides</i> (Kunth) P.H. Raven	Kleine waterteunisbloem	Jussie rampante	2016
<i>Lygodium japonicum</i> (Thunb.) Sw.	Japane klimvaren	Fougère grimpante du japon	2019*
<i>Lysichiton americanus</i> Hultén and St. John	Moerasaronkelk	Faux-arum	2016
<i>Marisa cornuarietis</i> (Linnaeus 1758)	Marisa slak	Marise corne-de-bélier	2025*

<i>Microstegium vimineum</i> (Trin.) A. Camus	Japans steltgras	Herbe à échasses japonaise	2017
<i>Misgurnus anguillicaudatus</i> (Cantor, 1842)	Aziatische modderkruiper	Loche baromètre	2025
<i>Misgurnus bipartitus</i> (Sauvage & Dabry de Thiersant, 1874)	Noord-Aziatische modderkruiper	Loche nord-asiatique	2025
<i>Morone americana</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	Amerikaanse baars	Bar blanc d'Amérique	2022
<i>Mulinia lateralis</i> (Say, 1822)	Amerikaanse strandschelp	Mactre naine	2025
<i>Muntiacus reevesi</i> Ogilby, 1839	Muntjak	Muntjac de Chine	2016
<i>Myocastor coypus</i> Molina, 1782	Beverrat	Ragondin	2016
<i>Myriophyllum aquaticum</i> (Vell.) Verdc.	Parelvederkruid	Myriophylle du Brésil	2016
<i>Myriophyllum heterophyllum</i> Michaux	Ongelijkbladig vederkruid	Myriophylle hétérophylle	2017
<i>Nanozostera japonica</i> (Ascherson & Graebner) Tomlinson & Posluszny, 2001	Japans dwergzee gras	Zostère du Japon	2025
<i>Nasua nasua</i> Linnaeus, 1766	Rode neusbeer	Coati roux	2016*
<i>Neogale vison</i> (Schreber, 1777)	Amerikaanse nerts	Vison d'Amérique	2025
<i>Nyctereutes procyonoides</i> Gray, 1834	Wasbeerhond	Chien viverrin	2017
<i>Obama nungara</i> Carbayo, Álvarez-Presas, Jones & Riutort, 2016	Grote gevlekte landplatworm	Ver plat d'Argentine	2025
<i>Ondatra zibethicus</i> Linnaeus, 1766	Muskusrat	Rat musqué	2017
<i>Oxyura jamaicensis</i> Gmelin, 1789	Rosse stekelstaart	Erismature rousse	2016
<i>Pacifastacus leniusculus</i> Dana, 1852	Californische rivierkreeft	Ecrevisse signal	2016
<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.	Schijnambrosia	Fausse camomille	2016*
<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> (Forssk.) Chiov.	Lampenpoetsersgras	Herbe aux écouvillons pourpres	2017*
<i>Percottus glenii</i> Dybowski, 1877	Amoergrondel	Goujon de l'Amour	2016
<i>Persicaria perfoliata</i> (L.)	Gstekelde duizendknoop	Renouée perfoliée	2016
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i> L.	Watersla	Laitue d'eau	2024*
<i>Platydemus manokwari</i> de Beauchamp, 1963	Nieuw-Guineese landplatworm	Ver plat de Nouvelle-Guinée	2025*
<i>Plotosus lineatus</i> (Thunberg, 1787)	Gestreepte koraalmeerval	Poisson-chat rayé	2019*
<i>Pontederia crassipes</i> (Mart.)	Waterhyacint	Jacinthe d'eau	2016*
<i>Procambarus clarkii</i> Girard, 1852	Rode Amerikaanse rivierkreeft	Ecrevisse de Louisiane	2016
<i>Procambarus virginalis</i> Lyko, 2017	Marmerkreeft	Ecrevisse marbrée	2016

<i>Procyon lotor</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Wasbeer	Raton laveur	2016
<i>Prosopis juliflora</i> (Sw.) DC	Mesquite	bayahonde	2019*
<i>Pseudorasbora parva</i> Temminck & Schlegel, 1846	Blauwbandgrondel	Goujon de Chine	2016
<i>Pueraria montana</i> (Lour.) Merr. var. lobata (Willd.)	Kudzu	Kudzu	2016*
<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Roodbuikbulbul	Bulbul à ventre rouge	2022*
<i>Pycnonotus jocosus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Roodoorbulbul	Bulbul orphée	2025*
<i>Reynoutria japonica</i> Houtt.	Japane duizendknoop	Renouée du Japon	2025
<i>Reynoutria sachalinensis</i> (F. Schmidt) Nakai	Sachalinse duizendknoop	Renouée de Sakhaline	2025
<i>Reynoutria × bohemica</i> Chrtek & Chrtková	Basterdduizendknoop	Renouée de Bohême	2025
<i>Rugulopterix okamurae</i> (E.Y.Dawson) I.K. Hwang, W.J.Lee & H.S.Kim, 2009	Stomp gaffelwier	Algue brune du Japon	2022*
<i>Salvinia molesta</i> D.S. Mitch. (<i>Salvinia adnata</i> Desv.)	Grote vlotvaren	Salvinie géante	2019*
<i>Sciurus carolinensis</i> Gmelin, 1788	Grijze eekhoorn	Ecureuil gris	2016
<i>Sciurus niger</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Amerikaanse voseekhoorn	Ecureuil fauve	2016
<i>Solenopsis geminata</i> (Fabricius, 1804)	Tropische vuurmier	Fourmi de feu tropicale	2022*
<i>Solenopsis invicta</i> Buren, 1972	Rode vuurmier	Grande fourmi de feu	2022*
<i>Solenopsis richteri</i> Forel, 1909	Zwarte vuurmier	Fourmi de feu noire	2022*
<i>Tamias sibiricus</i> Laxmann, 1769	Siberische grondeekhoorn	Tamias de Sibérie	2016
<i>Threskiornis aethiopicus</i> Latham, 1790	Heilige ibis	Ibis sacré	2016
<i>Trachemys scripta</i> Schoepff	Lettersierschildpad	Tortue de Floride	2016
<i>Triadica sebifera</i> (L.) Small (<i>Sapium sebiferum</i> (L.) Roxb.)	Talgboom	Arbre a suif	2019*
<i>Vespa mandarinia</i> Smith, 1852	Japane reuzenhoornaar	Frelon géant japonais	2025
<i>Vespa velutina nigrithorax</i> de Buysson, 1905	Aziatische hoornaar	Frelon asiatique	2016
<i>Wasmannia auropunctata</i> (Roger, 1863)	Dwergvuurmier	Petite fourmi de feu	2022*
<i>Xenopus laevis</i> (Daudin, 1802)	Afrikaanse klauwkikker	Xénope lisse	2024

3.2. Pathway identification

3.2.1. Pathway categorization

To classify pathways, the definitions of the CBD classification according to Harrower et al. (2018) were used, supplemented with extra information received from the European Commission on the distinction between intentional and unintentional introductions.

In general, there are six principal pathways for IAS (Hulme et al., 2008; CBD 2014; Harrower et al. 2018): 1) release in nature, 2) escape from confinement, 3) transport-contaminant, 4) transport-stowaway, 5) corridor and 6) unaided. For these main pathways, different subcategories are identified (CBD, 2014; FIG 1).

In accordance with the regulatory requirement to prioritize pathways of unintentional introduction and spread, the principal pathway “release in nature” was excluded from the analysis, as it constitutes an intentional pathway. Activities such as the release of animals by irresponsible owners or the disposal of garden material leading to the release of plants were, following clarification by the European Commission, classified under the pathway “escape” and were therefore retained for analysis.

- 1) **Release in nature** refers to the intentional introduction of live alien organisms for the purpose of human use in the natural environment. Examples include release in nature of organisms for biological control, erosion control (and dune stabilization), for fishing or hunting in the wild; landscape “improvement” and introduction of threatened organisms for conservation purposes.
- 2) **Escape** refers to the movement of (potentially) invasive alien species from confinement (e.g. in zoos, aquaria, botanic gardens, agriculture, horticulture, aquaculture and mariculture facilities; scientific research or breeding programs) into the natural environment. In this pathway, the organisms were initially purposefully imported or transported to be held in a “captive setting”, and then escaped (e.g. escape of live bait from a fishing line). Their presence in the environment is therefore considered accidental. Following clarification by the European Commission (pers. com), this pathway also includes the release of pets or the disposal of plants into the environment.
- 3) **Contaminant** refers to the unintentional movement of live organisms as contaminants of a commodity that is intentionally transferred through international trade, development assistance, or emergency relief. This includes pests and diseases of food, seeds, timber and other products of agriculture, forestry, and fisheries as well as contaminants of other products.
- 4) **Stowaway** refers to the movement of live organisms attached to transporting vessels and associated equipment and media. The physical means of transport-stowaway include various conveyances, ballast water and sediments, biofouling of ships, boats, offshore oil and gas platforms and other water vessels, dredging, angling or fishing equipment, civil aviation, sea and air containers.
- 5) **Corridor** refers to movement of alien organisms into a new region following the construction of transport infrastructures in whose absence spread would not have been possible. Such trans-biogeographical corridors include international canals (connecting

river catchments and seas) and transboundary tunnels linking mountain valleys or oceanic islands.

- 6) **Unaided** refers to the secondary natural dispersal of IAS that have been introduced by means of any of the foregoing pathways. Secondary natural dispersal (unaided) takes place after introduction via other pathways through human intervention. Information on the mechanisms of secondary spread of IAS, after their introduction, are relevant to define the best response measures.

Figure 1. CBD pathway categories and subcategories, adapted from Harrower et al., 2018. “Release in nature” was considered as an intentional pathway and not retained in the current pathway analysis, whereas the other listed categories and subcategories were considered. Release of pets or inadequate disposal of plants by irresponsible owners was considered under the “escape from confinement pathway”.

3.2.2. Inventory of species' specific pathways

In this study, pathways of introduction of Union List species were retrieved from published sources which are mainly based on available pathway information in the European risk assessments, supplemented with information from the DAISIE and GRISS database (Saul et al., 2017), the CABI Invasive Species Compendium, pathway information in the European risk assessments, and available pathway data or analysis performed in other Member States (CLM, 2010; Madsen et al., 2014; Ministère du Développement durable et des Infrastructures, Luxembourg, 2016; Rabitsch et al., 2018; van Veenhuisen et al., 2024).

This information was reviewed to assess the relevance of the pathways for the Belgian territory by expert review. For plants, popularity in the ornamental sector was also verified with the sector and via the website *plantago.nl*. For animals, information on permits for research, the presence in zoo collections and popularity of the species as pets was acquired from the regional animal welfare departments. Additionally, the information on the pathways (Brunel, 2009; Roy et al., 2013; Gallardo et al., 2016; Adriaens, 2016; Nunes et al., 2015; Carboneras et al., 2017; Saul et al., 2017) was also taken into account.

Pathways of spread for Union List IAS were considered alongside introduction pathways and analyzed jointly. Additionally, a separate analysis was conducted for species that are currently absent from Belgium, enabling a clearer identification of priority introduction pathways for these species.

3.3. Pathway prioritization

3.3.1. Identification of species' impacts

Article 13 requires Member States to: "...identify the pathways which require priority action because of the volume of species or of the potential damage caused by the species entering the Union through those pathways." To assess the magnitude of impact (damage) of an invasive alien species, we allocated a "risk-score" (from 1-12) to every species as a proxy for species impact. The calculation of these scores was based on the environmental impact protocol "ISEIA" (Invasive Species Environmental Impact Assessment; Branquart et al, 2009; Vanderhoeven et al., 2015). This protocol was developed to classify alien species according to their level of impact in Belgium and allocate alien species to the different hazard categories of the Harmonia information system¹ in an attempt to minimize the use of subjective opinions and to warrant the transparency and repeatability of the assessment process (Daehler et al., 2004, Vanderhoeven et al., 2017).

The allocation of scores to individual species is based on semi-quantitative scores for four different elements of impact. It takes into account four criteria, matching the last steps of the invasion process: (i) dispersal potential, (ii) colonization of natural habitats, (iii) adverse ecological impacts on native species, (iv) alteration of ecosystem functions. A score for these four criteria (i-iv) was attributed based on species information in literature and databases.

¹ <http://ias.biodiversity.be>

The ISEIA protocol was originally developed to assess species capable of establishing in Belgium under the current climatic conditions. However, because species of Union concern differ in their establishment potential, this analysis includes an explicit assessment of the “establishment potential”, which is used to weight the “dispersal potential” component in the scoring formula. and used it to weigh variable “dispersal potential” in the formula. This approach enables the calculation of an ISEIA score for species that are not (fully) able to establish under current climatic conditions, while maintaining full compatibility with ISEIA scores derived in past and future assessments for species already established in Belgium. Establishment potential was evaluated using a five-point scale ranging from one to five. A score of one indicates that the species cannot establish in Belgium under current nor future climatic conditions (e.g. *Prosopis juliflora*, a (sub)tropical species) whereas a score of five indicates that a species is able to establish under current climatic conditions (e.g. *Eriocheir sinensis*, already established in Belgium for over a century). The establishment potential scores for all species considered in this analysis are provided in Table 2. These values were assigned based upon expert consultation and a review of scientific literature.

The ISEIA score which accounts for establishment potential in Belgium, is hereafter referred to as the “Belgian ISEIA score” throughout this assessment. It is calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{BE ISEIA} = & \text{Colonisation of high value area} + \text{Impact} \\ & + \text{Alteration of ecosystem functions} + (\text{Dispersal potential} \\ & * \text{Establishment potential})/5 \end{aligned}$$

The ecological impact assessment score and the score for establishment potential (as described above) are both integrated in the pathway prioritization formula. As a result, pathways of introduction and spread associated with species that are unlikely to establish in Belgium are assigned lower priority. “Belgian ISEIA scores” were already available for 54 of the 114 species of the Union List species (ias.biodiversity.be). These existing scores were reviewed, validated and adapted where necessary in the light of newly available information.

3.3.2. Assessment of the frequency of introduction pathways

Article 13 requires Member States to: “...identify the pathways which require priority action because of the volume of species or of the potential damage caused by the species entering the Union through those pathways.” The “volume”, which can be interpreted as propagule pressure, as set out in the EU IAS Regulation was found to be difficult to assess due to the limited availability of reliable, quantitative pathway data (see also Adriaens, 2016 and Pergl et al., 2020). Furthermore, interception data is often biased (Worm et al., 2024) – as inspections may preferentially detect pest species that are familiar to inspectors, more visible organisms on traded goods, or commodities often containing pests that are subject to more frequent inspection.

To address these limitations, a simplified proxy for volume was applied by assessing the frequency of introduction of the species via each identified pathway. For each species-pathway combination, the frequency of introduction or spread was evaluated and classified into three categories, following a precautionary approach (Table 3). When the pathway was mentioned

in international literature, but its relevance for Belgium could not be confirmed, a score (0.33) was assigned instead of a zero, ensuring all potentially relevant pathways were retained in the analysis. All scores for the frequency of use of each pathway per species are available in Annex 1 of the report. For the pathway “escape”, the scoring accounted for the historical popularity of the species withing the domestic Belgian trade.

The pathway frequency category that was allocated to a certain species for a specific pathway, was further complemented with a confidence level (high, medium, low):

- **High confidence:** evidence of frequency is available.
- **Medium confidence:** there is limited evidence on frequency available from published information or observations, and the assessment is mainly based on expert judgment.
- **Low confidence:** there is no direct evidence on frequency available, and the assessment is fully based upon expert judgment.

In cases where the level of confidence was low, and no clear decision could be made regarding the allocation of a species to one of the three categories, the species was assigned to the “low” category. When some information was available, but uncertainty remained (e.g. between “low” and “medium”) the species was assigned the “medium” category. These confidence levels are not used in current analysis.

Table 2. Establishment potential (ESTAB) and Belgian ISEIA scores for the species included in the analysis. Establishment potential is scored on a five-point scale: 1 = unlikely to establish in Belgium under current or future climatic conditions (CC, FC); 2 = marginally able to establish under future climatic conditions; 3 = able to establish under future climatic conditions; 4 = marginally able to establish under current climatic conditions; 5 = able to establish under current climatic conditions.

Species	ESTAB.	BE ISEIA	Species	ESTAB.	BE ISEIA
<i>Acacia mearnsii</i>	3	11	<i>Lithobates catesbeianus</i>	5	12
<i>Acacia saligna</i>	3	11	<i>Ludwigia grandiflora</i>	5	12
<i>Acridotheres cristatellus</i>	5	8	<i>Ludwigia peploides</i>	5	12
<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	4	7	<i>Lygodium japonicum</i>	2	9
<i>Ailanthus altissima</i>	5	12	<i>Lysichiton americanus</i>	5	10
<i>Alopochen aegyptiacus</i>	5	12	<i>Marisa cornuarietis</i>	3	10
<i>Alternanthera philoxeroides</i>	3	11	<i>Microstegium vimineum</i>	5	12
<i>Ameiurus melas</i>	5	8	<i>Misgurnus anguillicaudatus</i>	5	11
<i>Andropogon virginicus</i>	2	9	<i>Misgurnus bipartitus</i>	5	11
<i>Arthurdendyus triangulatus</i>	5	10	<i>Morone americana</i>	5	8
<i>Asclepias syriaca</i>	5	12	<i>Mulinia lateralis</i>	5	9
<i>Asterias amurensis</i>	5	11	<i>Muntiacus reevesi</i>	5	12
<i>Axis axis</i>	5	10	<i>Myocastor coypus</i>	5	12
<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i>	5	12	<i>Myriophyllum aquaticum</i>	5	12
<i>Bipalium kewense</i>	5	8	<i>Myriophyllum heterophyllum</i>	5	12
<i>Brachyponera chinensis</i>	2	8	<i>Nanozostera japonica</i>	5	12
<i>Brousonettia papyrifera</i>	5	9	<i>Nasua nasua</i>	3	9
<i>Cabomba caroliniana</i>	5	10	<i>Neogale vison</i>	5	11
<i>Callosciurus erythraeus</i>	5	11	<i>Nyctereutes procyonoides</i>	5	9
<i>Callosciurus finlaysonii</i>	2	8	<i>Obama nungara</i>	5	10
<i>Cardiospermum grandiflorum</i>	3	11	<i>Ondatra zibethicus</i>	5	12
<i>Castor canadensis</i>	5	10	<i>Oxyura jamaicensis</i>	5	10
<i>Celastrus orbiculatus</i>	5	11	<i>Pacifastacus leniusculus</i>	5	12
<i>Cervus nipon</i>	5	12	<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i>	2	5
<i>Channa argus</i>	5	12	<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>	2	9
<i>Cherax destructor</i>	3	11	<i>Perccottus glenii</i>	5	11
<i>Cipangopaludina chinensis</i>	5	10	<i>Persicaria perfoliata</i>	5	11
<i>Cortaderia jubata</i>	5	12	<i>Pistia stratiotes</i>	2	10
<i>Corvus splendens</i>	5	7	<i>Platydemus manokwari</i>	2	10
<i>Crassula helmsii</i>	5	12	<i>Plotosus lineatus</i>	1	7
<i>Delairea odorata</i>	5	11	<i>Pontederia crassipes</i>	1	8
<i>Ehrharta cacycina</i>	2	10	<i>Procambarus clarkii</i>	5	12
<i>Elodea nuttallii</i>	5	12	<i>Procambarus virginalis</i>	5	12
<i>Eriocheir sinensis</i>	5	12	<i>Procyon lotor</i>	5	11
<i>Faxonius immunis</i>	5	12	<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	1	9

<i>Faxonius limosus</i>	5	12	<i>Pseudorasbora parva</i>	5	11
<i>Faxonius rusticus</i>	5	12	<i>Pueraria lobata</i>	3	10
<i>Faxonius virilis</i>	5	12	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	1	6
<i>Fundulus heteroclitus</i>	5	10	<i>Pycnonotus jocosus</i>	2	6
<i>Gambusia affinis</i>	5	11	<i>Reynoutria japonica</i>	5	12
<i>Gambusia holbrooki</i>	5	11	<i>Reynoutria sachalinensis</i>	5	12
<i>Gunnera tinctoria</i>	3	10	<i>Reynoutria × bohemica</i>	5	12
<i>Gymnocoronis spilanthoides</i>	4	11	<i>Rugulopterix okamurae</i>	2	10
<i>Hakea sericea</i>	4	11	<i>Salvinia molesta</i>	3	11
<i>Heracleum mantegazzianum</i>	5	10	<i>Sciurus carolinensis</i>	5	11
<i>Heracleum persicum</i>	5	11	<i>Sciurus niger</i>	5	9
<i>Heracleum sosnowskyi</i>	4	10	<i>Solenopsis geminata</i>	1	5
<i>Herpestes javanicus</i>	3	8	<i>Solenopsis invicta</i>	1	7
<i>Humulus scandens</i>	3	10	<i>Solenopsis richteri</i>	1	6
<i>Hydrocotyle ranunculoides</i>	5	12	<i>Tamias sibiricus</i>	5	9
<i>Impatiens glandulifera</i>	5	12	<i>Threskiornis aethiopicus</i>	5	11
<i>Koenigia polystachya</i>	5	10	<i>Trachemys scripta</i>	2	7
<i>Lagarosiphon major</i>	5	12	<i>Triadica sebifera</i>	3	11
<i>Lampropeltis getula</i>	1	6	<i>Vespa mandarinia</i>	5	12
<i>Lepomis gibbosus</i>	5	9	<i>Vespa velutina nigrithorax</i>	5	12
<i>Lespedeza cuneata</i>	5	11	<i>Wasmannia auropunctata</i>	1	7
<i>Limnoperna fortunei</i>	3	11	<i>Xenopus laevis</i>	5	10

Table 3. Frequency-categories used as a proxy for the volume of a species along the pathways of introduction and spread for Belgium.

Frequency	Category description	Score
Absent to low (1)	The pathway is infrequently used by the species or even not at all, it is unlikely (but possible) that the pathway is relevant for the species. Very few cases are described in literature. Very few observations are being made of this species in the pathway.	0,33
Medium (2)	The pathway is regularly being used by the species. Several cases are described in literature. Observations of the species in the pathway are regular but not common.	0,66
High (3)	The pathway is commonly used by the species and represents the main pathway of entry. Most cases in literature are observed in this pathway. Observations of this species in the pathway are common. e.g. <i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i> is a common seed contaminant in bird food. e.g. Several references in literature describe the high dispersal ability of Asian Hornet, <i>Vespa velutina</i> . The pathway “Natural dispersal” will score 1 for this species.	1,00

3.3.3. Pathway prioritization

Priority pathways are defined under Article 13 of the European IAS regulation as “pathways requiring action by priority because of the volume of the alien species using it or of the potential damage of these species”.

Prioritization involves two main steps: 1) ranking pathways according to their relative environmental impact (and where relevant socio-economic impact; sensu Blackburn et al., 2014), in order to identify those posing the greatest threat, and 2) assessing which pathways are manageable and offer the greatest potential for effective mitigation. The present report addresses the first step, focusing on the prioritization of pathways based on their impact.

To prioritize pathways, we followed an approach that integrates species impact and frequency of introduction per pathway, in line with the requirements of the EU IAS Regulation. Pathways are ranked using a formula that takes incorporates: (1) the number of species associated with the pathway, (2) the relative ecological impact of these species (expressed as the BE-ISEIA score divided by the average BE-ISEIA score) and (3) the frequency of introduction and spread (as a proxy for volume – see 5.3.2). The formula, which calculates the pathway priority score is calculated as follows:

$$\textit{Pathway priority score} = \sum \textit{Species} \left(\left[\frac{\textit{BE ISEIA score}}{10} \right] * [\textit{Pathway frequency}] \right)$$

By definition, the ISEIA scores for ecological impact of Union List species are rather high. In the present dataset, these scores are weighted by establishment potential, which can substantially reduce overall values. While scores can theoretically range from 4 to 12, the scores in this dataset range between 4,5 and 12 with a median of 11 and a mean value of 10. To ensure compatibility, scores were normalized in line with the scale used for pathway frequency. The confidence levels associated with the frequency scores (high – medium – low) was not considered in this exercise but can be used as an additional factor in the decision-making process on which priority pathways to tackle.

The application of the formula is illustrated with an example in Table 4 :

- The simple summation of the number of species associated with a hypothetical pathway yields a pathway score of 12.
- When species impact (I) alone is considered, the hypothetical pathway score increases to 13, reflecting the presence of species with relatively high impact values (>1).
- When jointly considering species impact and species frequency, the overall pathway score decreases due to the relatively high proportion of species with low to medium scores for pathway frequency (<1).

Table 4. Example to illustrate the calculation of the priority score of a hypothetical pathway. Species impact (BE ISEIA/average BE ISEIA) ; Frequency: a proxy for the volume of the species on the pathway: low (0,33), medium (0,66) high (1).

	<u>Impact (I)</u>	<u>Frequency (V)</u>	<u>I × V</u>
Species 1	0,9	0,33	0,297
Species 2	1,0	0,66	0,660
Species 3	1,1	1,00	1,100
Species 4	1,2	1,00	1,200
Species 5	0,9	0,33	0,297
Species 6	1,0	0,66	0,660
Species 7	1,2	0,33	0,396
Species 8	1,2	0,33	0,396
Species 9	1,2	0,33	0,396
Species 10	1,0	0,66	0,660
Species 11	1,1	0,33	0,363
Species 12	1,2	0,33	0,396
$\Sigma(\text{spp.}) = 12$	$\Sigma(I) = 13$		$\Sigma(I \times V) = 6,821$

4. Results

4.1. Pathway identification

General description

A total of 27 out of the 33 potential pathways of introduction and spread were identified for the 114 species of Union concern, representing 4 out of 5 main unintentional pathway categories: unaided, escape from confinement, transport stowaway and transport contaminant (TABLE 5; FIG 2).

The relevance of pathways varied considerably across the dataset, with some pathways associated with a large number of species and others only with a few. For example, natural dispersal and escape of pet/aquarium/terrarium species were identified as a pathway of introduction or spread for more than half of the species considered. Pathways such as the escape of animal species from zoos, escape of plant species, and contaminant of transport of habitat material were each relevant for approximately one third of the species in the dataset. In contrast, escape from confinement in research and forestry, and transport as contaminant of timber trade were relevant for maximum three species. It is important to note that the low importance -or apparent absence- of certain pathways in this analysis is not because these pathways are insignificant in the Belgian context. Rather, this reflects a bias resulting from the limited number and composition of species on the Union list. For instance, while marine pathways are globally recognised as major routes of unintentional introduction, pathways such as hull fouling and ballast water do not rank highly in this assessment because of the limited representation of marine species on the Union list.

Description by species groups

When looking at species groups (aquatic animals, aquatic plants, terrestrial plants, birds, mammals, reptiles and amphibians and terrestrial invertebrates; FIG 3A-B), only one pathway – unaided – was relevant across all groups. In addition, escape from private premises (including pet/aquarium/terrarium; escape ornamental other than horticulture; escape from zoo/aquaria/botanical garden) was identified as relevant for all groups, although its importance was comparatively limited for the terrestrial invertebrates.

Beyond escape pathways, terrestrial plants were also implicated in all categories of contaminant pathways identified for Belgium with the exception of contaminated bait. They were also associated with several stowaway pathways, including “vehicles”, “machinery”, “luggage” and “angling and fishing equipment” – likely due to contamination by seeds or vegetative fragments. Aquatic plants shared many introduction and spread pathways with their terrestrial counterparts, though they were excluded from transport or contaminant pathways linked more to terrestrial activities such as “stowaway on luggage and vehicles” and included in more aquatic transport and contaminant pathways such as “hitchhiker on boats”, “hull fouling” and “ballast water”.

Overall, individual animal groups were involved in fewer introduction pathways than plant groups, though this could also reflect the higher degree of group splitting among animals. Overall, the animals feature in 22 out of 33 pathways and the plants in 20 out of 33. Apart from escape pathways – some of which unique to the mammals (e.g. fur farms, farmed animals) – mammals are only associated with the stowaway pathway “container” and “ship/boat”. Birds were implicated in even less pathways – only escapes from zoos or as pets and stowaway on boats. Reptiles and amphibians were similarly restricted, mainly to escape from captivity (zoos or pets). Amphibians were also implicated in escape from research facilities, and tadpoles could occur as contaminants of aquatic animals. Reptiles could occur as a contaminant of plants or as a stowaway on a ship/boat.

Aquatic animals are a relatively diverse group (vertebrates and invertebrates) and were uniquely implicated in a few escape pathways such as “aquaculture”, “live food and bait” in addition to escapes from zoos and aquaria. They were also involved in three contaminant pathways (on animals, on plants and in habitat material) and four stowaway pathways (angling/fishing equipment, ballast, hull, ship/boat).

For terrestrial invertebrates, a total of 10 pathways were identified: four transport contaminant pathways (food, nursery and habitat material, and timber), four transport stowaway pathways (container, airplane, machinery, vehicles) and two escape from confinement pathways (pet/aquarium/terrarium and live food).

4.2. Pathway prioritization

The prioritisation analysis identifies natural dispersal as the highest ranked pathway (Table 5), with a pronounced decline in cumulative species impact for the second ranked pathway “escape from confinement”. This is not surprising since we not only assessed pathways of introduction but also considered pathways of spread in parallel. Unlike other pathways, introduction into or spread within Belgium through “natural dispersal” applies to a large number of species, thereby increasing its prominence in the ranking.

Pathways associated with the escape or disposal of pets, garden plants and zoo species

occupy ranks 2, 3 and 5, underscoring the importance of escape pathways in the introduction and spread of IAS. Notably, escape from zoos and botanic gardens accounts for only half of the cumulative impact of species compared to the escape of pets from private owners and roughly two-thirds of the impact of escapes from plants from gardens or public greenery.

“Transport of habitat material” ranks 4th, representing the contaminant pathway with the highest cumulative species impact. The pathways **stowaway on machinery**”, “stowaway on **angling/fishing material**” and “**contaminant of nursery material**” rank 6th, 7th and 8th respectively, with relatively similar cumulative impacts. Ranks 9 and 10, are the pathways “**hitchhikers on ships/boats**” and “**contaminant on animals**”, each with cumulative impacts of roughly one-third of the impact from the second ranked pathway “escape of pet/aquarium/terrarium species”. From “**contaminant on plants**” (rank 11th, cumulative impact 9.1), there is a gradual decline in cumulative impacts across the next 16 pathways ultimately reaching a minimum of 0.3.

Figure 2. Pathway ranking for the 114 species of Union concern, based on a composite score combining cumulative impact and introduction frequency (pathway volume), with the number of species associated with each pathway also indicated.

Table 5. Pathway ranking for the 114 species of Union concern based on a composite metric of cumulative impact * volume (frequency of introduction for the species in a pathway) of the species using each pathway. The number of species associated with each is also indicated.

Pathway category	Pathway	Σ Impact x volume	Nb of species
Unaided	Natural dispersal	52,3	67
Escape from confinement	Pet/aquarium/terrarium	40,6	57
Escape from confinement	Ornamental purposes	29,3	38
Transport contaminant	Transport. of habitat material	22,4	36
Escape from confinement	Botanical garden/zoo/aquaria	18,7	36
Transport stowaway	Machinery	16,9	27
Transport stowaway	Angling/fishing equipment	16,8	24
Transport contaminant	Contaminant nursery material	15,3	24
Transport stowaway	Hitchhikers on ship/boat	13,4	19
Transport contaminant	Contaminant on animals	12,3	21
Transport contaminant	Contaminant on plants	9,1	17
Escape from confinement	Live food and live bait	6,6	14
Transport stowaway	Ballast	5,6	9
Transport stowaway	Container	4,5	8
Escape from confinement	Aquaculture	3,0	6
Transport stowaway	Luggage	2,7	7
Transport stowaway	Hull	2,5	4
Escape from confinement	Farmed animals	2,3	5
Transport stowaway	Vehicles	2,2	6
Transport contaminant	Seed contaminant	1,5	4
Escape from confinement	Fur farms	1,5	4
Escape from confinement	Agriculture	1,4	4
Transport stowaway	Hitchhikers in or on airplanes	1,1	5
Transport contaminant	Food contaminant	1,1	3
Escape from confinement	Research	1,0	2
Transport contaminant	Timber trade	0,9	3
Escape from confinement	Forestry	0,3	1

Figure 3A. Pathways ranking for the 114 species of Union concern by species group: Part 1 - "Aquatic plants" and "terrestrial plants"

Figure 3B. Pathways ranking for the 114 species of Union concern according by species group: Part 2 - "aquatic animals", "birds", "terrestrial invertebrates", "mammals" and "reptiles and amphibians"

Comparison with previous prioritisation analyses (66 and 88 species)

There was **no new pathway identified** compared to the previous analysis with 88 species. The **top 12 pathways for the 114 species are consistent with those reported in the previous prioritizations based on 66 species and 88 species** (Table 6). While the ranking of the top 3 remained unchanged, minor shifts in rank were observed among the remaining top 12. Notably, “transport of habitat material” and “stowaway on machinery”, each increased by two positions in the ranking. Conversely, pathways linked to aquatic stowaways, specifically those on angling equipment and on ships show a slight decrease in rank.

Beyond this top 12, the pathways **“transport stowaways of ballasts” and transport stowaways in containers”** – which had increased in importance in the previous prioritization – maintained their position at 13th and 14th place respectively.

Table 6. Comparison between pathway ranks following impact-based prioritization across datasets comprising 66, 88 and 114 species.

	Prioritization 66 species	$\sum I \times V$	Prioritization 88 species	$\sum I \times V$	Prioritization 114 species	$\sum I \times V$	
1	Natural dispersal	37,5	Natural dispersal	41,8	Natural dispersal	52,3	
2	Pet/aquarium/terrarium	26,2	Pet/aquarium/terrarium	31,1	Pet/aquarium/terrarium	40,6	
3	Ornamental purposes	21,6	Ornamental purposes	24,4	Ornamental purposes	29,3	
4	Angling/fishing equipment	13,5	Botanical garden/zoo/aquaria	15,7	Transport. of habitat material	22,4	↑
5	Botanical garden/zoo/aquaria	13,3	Angling/fishing equipment	15,6	Botanical garden/zoo/aquaria	18,7	↓
6	Transport. of habitat material	12,8	Transport. of habitat material	14,0	Machinery	16,9	↑
7	Hitchhikers on ship/boat	11	Contaminant nursery material	11,9	Angling/fishing equipment	16,8	↓
8	Machinery	9,9	Hitchhikers on ship/boat	11,3	Contaminant nursery material	15,3	
9	Contaminant nursery material	9,5	Contaminant on animals	10,8	Hitchhikers on ship/boat	13,4	↓
10	Contaminant on animals	7,4	Machinery	9,9	Contaminant on animals	12,3	
11	Contaminant on plants	6,0	Contaminant on plants	6,9	Contaminant on plants	9,1	
12	Live food and live bait	4,3	Live food and live bait	5,0	Live food and live bait	6,6	

Prioritization for species that are not yet established

An additional analysis was conducted on the subset of species not yet established in Belgium (71 species out of the 114 Union list species) to better identify priority pathways for preventing new introductions. However, these results should be interpreted as indicative rather than providing a precise assessment of pathways strictly associated with new introductions into Belgium. The relevance of the pathway (or sector) in Belgium is indeed not considered in the calculations, and it is also challenging to assign different scores to pathways depending on whether they function primarily in spread or introduction.

The prioritization based on the 71 species not yet present in Belgium reveals a few points:

- Natural dispersal remains high, indicating new introductions coming from an invasion front are very likely and cooperation with neighbouring countries should be sought to manage this issue.
- Four pathways, involving contaminated goods (contaminant nursery material and contaminant on animals) and international transport vectors (containers and ballast water) become more critical when considering species that are not yet present in the country.
- Pathways such as transport of habitat material, machinery, and recreational equipment remain important in both contexts but tend to be relatively less dominant when focusing strictly on new introductions.
- Pathways of escape from captivity (*i.e.* species intentionally brought into the country for use in a captive setting which later escape) remain very important.

Table 7. Comparison between pathway ranks after prioritization on impact for the dataset of 114 species, and for the subset of 71 species that are not yet established in Belgium.

Prioritization 114 species		$\sum I \times V$	Prioritization 71 absent species	$\sum I \times V$	
1	Natural dispersal	52,3	Pet/aquarium/terrarium	18,3	
2	Pet/aquarium/terrarium	40,6	Natural dispersal	11,6	
3	Ornamental purposes	29,3	Botanical garden/zoo/aquaria	11,5	
4	Transport. of habitat material	22,4	Contaminant nursery material	8,5	↑
5	Botanical garden/zoo/aquaria	18,7	Ornamental purposes	8,2	
6	Machinery	16,9	Contaminant on animals	6,3	↑
7	Angling/fishing equipment	16,8	Transport. of habitat material	5,8	
8	Contaminant nursery material	15,3	Machinery	4,3	
9	Hitchhikers on ship/boat	13,4	Container	4,1	↑
10	Contaminant on animals	12,3	Angling/fishing equipment	3,2	
11	Contaminant on plants	9,1	Ballast	3,1	↑
12	Live food and live bait	6,6	Hitchhikers on ship/boat	2,6	

5. Discussion

5.1. Update of the national action plan

A. The first national action plan on pathways of introduction and spread already encompasses the priority pathways identified in the present analysis. Consequently, it could be argued that the inclusion of additional pathways in the updated version of the Action plan is not strictly necessary. However, in the light of the increasing significance of the **container pathway** for species currently still absent from the territory, we recommend considering its inclusion in the plan (*cf* points B and C hereunder). Furthermore, given that **natural dispersal** was identified as the highest ranked pathway of introduction and spread for the species in this dataset, increased cooperation with neighbouring countries should be explored, especially with regard to coordinated management efforts. In parallel, enhanced alignment and coordination of management actions among the Belgian regions is also recommended.

Firstly, the current National action plan on priority pathways of unintentional introduction and spread of invasive alien species of the Union list in Belgium (hereafter mentioned as “National action plan”), structured into three thematic chapters, already includes actions addressing 10 of the 12 principal pathways identified in the present analysis (“Natural dispersal” and “Escape from botanical garden, zoo, aquaria”, were excluded following a policy decision). Importantly, **the subset of top 12 pathways - based on cumulative species impact – remains unchanged** compared to the earlier assessment of 66 species which underpinned the original development of the national action plan in 2022.

Secondly, the assessment of whether any important pathways for specific species groups are missing from the current action plan showed that the **highest-ranking pathways for all groups examined are already sufficiently covered**. They are either included in the previous action plan, deliberately excluded due to policy decisions (“natural dispersal” and “escape botanical garden/zoo/aquarium”), or addressed through other instruments outside the Action Plan (*e.g.* international ballast-water legislation, regional bans on fur farms, support for customs services in luggage controls).

Thirdly, although **no additional pathways were identified** in the updated dataset (covering 114 species) as compared to the previous analysis, **two key points of attention emerge when focusing on species that are not yet present in Belgium:**

- First, the pathway “**natural dispersal**” is not only the most frequent pathway for the dataset as a whole, it is also the second most important pathway for the species still absent for Belgium. This highlights the **importance of strengthening cross-border cooperation with neighbouring countries**, alongside the development and deployment of a fit for purpose surveillance network at priority entry points. Such a network would facilitate early detections and enable timely implementation of rapid response measures aimed at preventing establishment within the Belgian territory.
- Second, **it should be noted that the pathways “container” is not covered by the current action plan**, despite its emerging relevance, particularly for species not yet present in Belgium. It is an important pathway (frequency scored as 0,66 or 1) for the

five ants and to a lesser extent for the Asian giant hornet (0,33). While these ant species are unlikely to establish outdoors under present climatic conditions and therefore pose limited direct risks to biodiversity or secondary spread to other Member States, caution is nevertheless warranted. A clear protocol for dealing with unwanted hitchhikers in freight containers should be established by the relevant authority, and enhanced monitoring to support detection of potential introductions of invasive terrestrial invertebrates should be implemented. However, increased monitoring in the field should be underpinned by robust prioritisation of inspections, which is dependent on data. It is therefore essential to invest in data generation and improved reporting of introduction events.

B. Although the priority pathways are covered by the current action plan, we recommend adding extra actions or extend the scope of current actions for some pathways that gained importance with the last two updates of the Union list. The new Union list species should also be included in the existing actions.

In general, the national action plan was designed with a process-oriented rather than a species-specific focus. Consequently, the existing measures are inherently broad in scope and address the risks of introduction and spread of a wide range of organisms across pathways, including newly added species. Examples include measures aimed at strengthening biosecurity, raising public awareness, increased capacity for managing the release or dumping of pets).

Nevertheless, we assessed whether additional actions are warranted for pathways that have increased in importance compared to the analysis on 66 and 88 species. Four pathways can be identified as having experienced a notable increase in their associated impact score:

- **Transportation of habitat material:** this pathway is already included in the thematic chapter of soil. Its increased importance is largely driven by the inclusion of the Asian knotweeds which are already a central focus in the development of the measures discussed in the soil working group. This renewed prioritisation further underlines the need for robust and consistently implemented prevention measures, particularly with regards to the handling, transport and disposal of contaminated soil. Strengthening guidance, enforcement and stakeholder engagement in this domain remains essential.
- **Machinery:** this pathway has thus far been primarily considered in relation to aquatic species. However, its growing relevance for terrestrial species suggests that the scope of existing measures should be expanded. This could include the development and implementation of biosecurity protocols for machinery used in terrestrial environments such as roadside mowing equipment and construction machinery.
- **Contaminant of nursery material:** this pathway is relevant for a total of **9 newly listed species** in the last two updates (ants and flatworms). Given that the ant species are not likely to be able to establish in Belgium under current climatic conditions, the development of additional measures for this group does not appear to be a priority. In contrast, for flatworms we recommend investing in the development of effective detection methods and implementation of targeted biosecurity measures in the

horticultural sector – in addition to the existing awareness raising measures included in the code of conduct for horticulture.

- **Contaminant on animals:** this pathway is relevant for a total of **10 aquatic species** listed in the last two updates and mainly concerns the **contamination of fish or mollusc imports and/or transports**. In this context, the findings of the baseline analysis on importation of aquatic animals (*ACTION 1 of Freshwater Action Plan*) should be reevaluated in the light of updated species list. Particular attention should be paid to the development and deployment of improved detection methods. In addition, the scope of the analysis and management measures should be broadened to explicitly include marine species, ensuring a more comprehensive and coherent approach across imported goods associated with aquatic environments – especially those that will be used in natural environments such as species imported for aquaculture purposes.

C. It may be appropriate to consider the inclusion of a dedicated thematic chapter on research and data generation to close knowledge gaps.

At present, empirical data on frequency and volume of species transported along certain unintentional pathways of introduction and spread is scarce. This is illustrated by the **limited availability of interception data linked to trade**. Even for traded species, existing systems often lack the level of detail required for robust pathway analysis (e.g. GN codes, TRACES data) while in other cases such systems are entirely absent. A notable example is the lack of systematic data on intra-Eu trade in ornamental plants which hampers the assessment of contamination risks associated with plant consignments. Establishing a more comprehensive overview of goods and their origin is a fundamental prerequisite for evaluating risks such as mislabelling and biological contamination.

In addition, **data on risks of introduction and spread of contaminants and hitchhikers, as well as the efficacy of measures are also largely lacking across several pathways**. This includes, for example, insufficient information on biofouling of hulls and ropes of (recreational) ships, on the transport of propagules via recreational aquatic gear (e.g. fishing rods or waders), on the presence of plant propagules at soil storage and transfer, on contamination of containers or on contaminants of nursery material. Such data are frequently requested by stakeholders as a basis for justifying investments in preventative measures, yet they remain limited or unavailable. The generation of such data is therefore critical to support evidence-based policy and to enhance the effectiveness of measures aimed at reducing unintentional introduction and spread. This challenge is further compounded by the lack of detection protocols, which constrains the ability to generate such data. Overall, the current lack of detailed trade data and quantitative information on propagule pressure across pathways represents a significant barrier to the development of more effective and proportionate policy measures.

It should, however, be acknowledged that not all data gaps can be addressed at the national level. Many relevant pathways—particularly those linked to international trade and transport—operate across borders, and key data should be generated, held, or regulated at the European or global scale. To mitigate this limitation, Belgium should actively engage in and promote international collaboration, including data sharing initiatives, harmonisation of monitoring and

reporting standards, and participation in joint research programmes. Leveraging existing European frameworks and agencies, and fostering cooperation with neighbouring countries, will be essential to improve access to relevant data and ensure coherence in pathway management.

5.2. Considerations and limitations

During the process of prioritizing pathways of introduction and spread of IAS of Union concern for Belgium, several considerations and limitations of the current analysis were identified. These points partly reiterate the knowledge gaps highlighted hereabove in section 5.1 (point C) and provide context for interpreting the results:

First, the present analysis does **not constitute a comprehensive pathway assessment for all IAS relevant for Belgium but is restricted to species included on the Union list**. While the inclusion of non-listed is not required by the EU IAS Regulation, expanding the scope could provide added value – especially for devising an action plan that has as much impact as possible for the Belgian biodiversity. Broadening the analysis to include a wider pool of alien species – such as those listed in existing inventories (e.g. Verleye et al., 2025; GRIIS checklist, Desmet et al., 2019) – would likely enhance preparedness for future invasions and increase the resilience of the action plans to updates of the Union list. However, careful consideration is needed when selecting such species pools. For example, focusing solely on species already present in Belgium (Desmet et al., 2019) would exclude emerging risks of species that are not yet established in Belgium. Moreover, broader analysis are inherently more resource intensive and less targeted than assessments focused on Union-listed species, which have undergone a rigorous scientific and policy evaluation.

Second, there remains substantial **uncertainty about the role and relative importance of specific pathways of introduction and spread for individual species**. In the case where no pathway information was available in literature or documents, expert opinion was used to assess pathway relevance. While the use of expert opinion is still necessary until more detailed and qualitative pathway data is available, this introduces a degree of subjectivity to the analysis.

Third, for several species, key ecological parameters remain insufficiently characterized. In particular, data on establishment potential under current and future climatic conditions is often lacking. For some species (e.g. *Cortaderia jubata*) there is little to no information on reproductive capacity such as seed production and germination rates, under Belgian conditions. Furthermore, assessing the potential ecological impact of species not established in Europe remains inherently uncertain. As new ecological and distributional data become available, it is therefore important to periodically revisit and where necessary revise pathway prioritization scores.

Finally, while the current analysis provides a useful basis for prioritization, it could be further refined if key knowledge gaps were addressed. For example, the integration of **historical and contemporary proxies for introduction effort as well as the analysis of spatio-temporal dynamics in pathways** would improve understanding of trends and emerging risks.

Distinguishing more clearly **between pathways of initial introduction into Belgium or Europe and pathways of subsequent spread within the region** (*i.e.* primary and secondary pathways see Pergl et al., 2020) would enable more targeted action plans and better prevention of new introductions or spread within Belgium. One could for example attribute more weight to introduction pathways of species not yet established in Belgium or make more precise distinctions within specific pathways (*e.g.* introduction via hull fouling is more likely for short boat travels within Europe near the coast than for transatlantic travels where the monetary implications of having a non-streamlined hull are much larger). However, such considerations are nearly impossible to incorporate before the analysis given the lack of data on certain pathways and would increase uncertainty.

As a concluding remark, it should be emphasized that, beyond the analytical limitations outlined above, the current process of pathway prioritization and intervention through action plans is notoriously slow. To ensure timely and effective responses to emerging risks, this process should be complemented by a more agile framework including rapid response mechanisms supported by contingency planning, similar to post-border incursions.

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7. Annex

Table presenting frequency-categories (as a proxy for volume) of use of all species in each pathway (light grey: 0,33 / grey: 0,66 / black: 1 / white: 0) – more information on the scores is available in Table 3.

Scientific name	Escape from confinement										Transport contaminant							Transport - stowaway							Unaided								
	Agriculture	Aquaculture	Botanical garden/zoo/aquaria	Pet/aquarium/terrarium	Farmed animals	Forestry	Fur farms	Horticulture	Ornamental	Research	Live food and live bait	Other escape from confinement	Contaminant nursery material	Contaminated bait	Food contaminant	Contaminant on animals	Contaminant on plants	Seed contaminant	Timber trade	Transportation of habitat material	Angling/fishing equipment	Container	Hitchhikers in or on airplanes	Hitchhikers on ship/boat		Machinery	Luggage	Organic packing material	Ballast	Hull	Vehicles	Other transport	Natural dispersal
PLANTS																																	
<i>Acacia mearnsii</i>																																	
<i>Acacia saligna</i>																																	
<i>Ailanthus altissima</i>																																	
<i>Alternanthera philoxeroides</i>																																	
<i>Andropogon virginicus</i>																																	
<i>Asclepias syriaca</i>																																	
<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i>																																	
<i>Broussonetia papyrifera</i>																																	
<i>Cabomba caroliniana</i>																																	
<i>Cardiospermum grandiflorum</i>																																	
<i>Celastrus orbiculatus</i>																																	
<i>Cortaderia jubata</i>																																	
<i>Crassula helmsii</i>																																	
<i>Delairea odorata</i>																																	
<i>Ehrharta calycina</i>																																	
<i>Elodea nuttallii</i>																																	
<i>Gunnera tinctoria</i>																																	
<i>Gymnocoronis spilanthoides</i>																																	
<i>Hakea sericea</i>																																	
<i>Heracleum mantegazzianum</i>																																	
<i>Heracleum persicum</i>																																	
<i>Heracleum sosnowskyi</i>																																	
<i>Humulus scandens</i>																																	
<i>Hydrocotyle ranunculoides</i>																																	
<i>Impatiens glandulifera</i>																																	
<i>Koenigia polystachya</i>																																	
<i>Lagarosiphon major</i>																																	
<i>Lespedeza cuneata</i>																																	
<i>Ludwigia grandiflora</i>																																	
<i>Ludwigia peploides</i>																																	
<i>Lygodium japonicum</i>																																	
<i>Lysichiton americanus</i>																																	
<i>Microstegium vimineum</i>																																	
<i>Myriophyllum aquaticum</i>																																	
<i>Myriophyllum heterophyllum</i>																																	
<i>Nanozostera japonica</i>																																	

Scientific name	Escape from confinement										Transport contaminant							Transport - stowaway							Unaided													
	Agriculture	Aquaculture	Botanical garden/zoo/aquaria	Pet/aquarium/terrarium	Farmed animals	Forestry	Fur farms	Horticulture	Ornamental	Research	Live food and live bait	Other escape from confinement	Contaminant nursery material	Contaminated bait	Food contaminant	Contaminant on animals	Contaminant on plants	Seed contaminant	Timber trade	Transportation of habitat material	Angling/fishing equipment	Container	Hitchhikers in or on airplanes	Hitchhikers on ship/boat		Machinery	Luggage	Organic packing material	Ballast	Hull	Vehicles	Other transport	Natural dispersal					
PLANTS																																						
<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i>																																						
<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>																																						
<i>Persicaria perfoliata</i>																																						
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i>																																						
<i>Pontederia crassipes</i>																																						
<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>																																						
<i>Pueraria lobata</i>																																						
<i>Reynoutria japonica</i>																																						
<i>Reynoutria sachalinensis</i>																																						
<i>Reynoutria × bohemica</i>																																						
<i>Rugulopteryx okamurae</i>																																						
<i>Salvinia molesta</i>																																						
<i>Triadica sebifera</i>																																						
ANIMALS																																						
<i>Acridotheres cristatellus</i>																																						
<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>																																						
<i>Alopochen aegyptiacus</i>																																						
<i>Ameiurus melas</i>																																						
<i>Arthurdendyyus triangulatus</i>																																						
<i>Asterias amurensis</i>																																						
<i>Axis axis</i>																																						
<i>Bipalium kewense</i>																																						
<i>Brachyponera chinensis</i>																																						
<i>Callosciurus erythraeus</i>																																						
<i>Callosciurus finlaysonii</i>																																						
<i>Castor canadensis</i>																																						
<i>Cervus nippon</i>																																						
<i>Channa argus</i>																																						
<i>Cherax destructor</i>																																						
<i>Cipangopaludina chinensis</i>																																						
<i>Corvus splendens</i>																																						
<i>Eriocheir chinensis</i>																																						
<i>Faxonius immnis</i>																																						
<i>Faxonius limosus</i>																																						
<i>Faxonius rusticus</i>																																						
<i>Faxonius virilis</i>																																						
<i>Fundulus heteroclitus</i>																																						
<i>Gambusia affinis</i>																																						
<i>Gambusia holbrooki</i>																																						
<i>Herpestes javanicus</i>																																						
<i>Lampropeltis getula</i>																																						

